

Grant Agreement N°763990

UPWARDS
Deliverable D8.2

Dissemination & Communication Management Plan

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Task	8.2	Dissemination & Communication Plan

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¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

² Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

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Deliverable abstract

The scope of present document is to comply with Consortium Commitment Deliverable D8.2, namely "UPWARDS Dissemination & Communication Plan". It describes the initial strategy sharing and promotion of information about the UPWARDS project among the professional community and industry stakeholders as well as the general public, at varying levels of detail and complexity. This includes the various activities to be done and channels to be used to communicate to each of the targeted groups.

As described in the UPWARDS GA, it will take into account the requirements for data integration and processing of UPWARDS virtual wind turbine. It will include information on how research data will be handled during and after the end of the project; what data will be collected, processed and/or generated; which methodology and standards will be applied; whether data will be shared/made open access and how data will be organized and accessible during and after the project.

The stakeholders will be engaged through the External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB), UPWARDS network will be reached through social media and interacting with user and interest groups at public events and conferences.

- External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB): these actors will have access to the open project information, but not confidential information. Still they will have to sign a specific NDA, which will be validated by the consortium as a whole and annexes to the Consortium Agreement;
- UPWARDS network: one of the main indicators of impact will be the number of stakeholders active in UPWARDS and giving feedback about the project outputs. Also, EEAB and stakeholders such as associations and working groups in EU platforms, will help boost UPWARDS's outreach, as multipliers.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and Scope

The motivation of this document is to provide a final overview on all the project dissemination and communication results. Dissemination and communication (D&C) of results is one of the major tasks for every European project. The dissemination actions from UPWARDS are aimed at communicating project results to a wide audience, fostering the adoption of project results and its impact.

The dissemination & communication in UPWARDS involves the coordination of all the activities being performed within WP-8 primarily handled by Wavestone with support by all partners.

UPWARDS looks to take an 'multi-modal' approach consisting of physical (face-to-face) communication, online communication and off-line written communication, with various channels being exploited in each of the 3 modes mentioned.

More specifically the channels in **face-to-face** D&C include technical exhibitions, scientific conferences and workshops. The majority of these face-to-face interactions will be with the professional and academic communities. Thus, one of the purposes of these interactions will be networking among research and educational organizations as this project has a relatively low TRL range. The other will be about establishing connections with industry players (such as in naval and aerospace) to pave the way for future applications of the solution and further impact of the project.

Offline UPWARDS D&C activities include journal publications, brochures and flyers. These will complement and be in addition to the face-to-face interactions that will take place.

Online D&C will occur through the UPWARDS website, through any corresponding news/promotional channels of the partnering organizations as well as the project's LinkedIn and Facebook pages. This will enable maximization of the number of people across as many countries as possible exposed to the purpose, progress and news on this project. Promoting awareness of the importance of the project and the industry as a whole will help set the tone for future discussions among society regarding Europe's energy future.

In order to further expand exposure and promotion of the UPWARDS project, links will be aimed to be created with external news organizations focused on the renewable/wind energy industry in order to publish articles written internally and/or encourage independent external reporting & coverage.

The scope of the audiences being targeted is quite comprehensive and consists of the scientific community, community stakeholders, industries related to wind energy, European platform, Associations, third parties/joint ventures, policy makers and EC authorities & Standardization & certification bodies

Progress in developing awareness and impact of the project will be tracked and quantified thanks to the measurables that will be recorded. Table 1 (below) shows a comprehensive list of possible measurables (KPIs) that can be used to track progress. A good number of these shall be used as needed for the UPWARDS project.

Item	Description	Related KPI(s)	Audience					Targets
			General audience	Civil society groups	Policy makers	Industry	Academics & research	

Actions	Organization of topic discussions (internal progress meetings)	# of discussions						X	Bi-weekly
	Organization of meetings with stakeholders	# of meetings	X	X	X	X	X		6 MEETINGS
	Participation to events: conferences, fairs, info sessions	# of events # of contacts made			X	X	X		14 events minimum 10 contacts made per event
	Media coverage online	# of entries # of likes # of retweets	X	X	X				10 entries 200 likes 50 retweets
	Open access publication	# of references				X	X		25 references
	Seminars	# of seminars # of attendees					X		8 seminars, 50-100 attendees per seminar
	Trainings, webinars' organization	# of trainings # of trainees # of feedback	X	X	X	X	X		4 trainings 50 trainees 50 feedback
	Workshop's organization	# of workshops # of participants	X		X	X	X		3 workshops 30 participants
Tools	Articles	# of articles	X	X	X	X	X	X	12
	Progress reports	# of reports						X	Every 18 months
	Presentations (in all types of events)	# of presentations # of attendees	X	X	X	X	X		15 presentations 300 attendees (total)
	Policy recommendations	# of reports		X	X				2 reports
	Website	Website statistics	X	X	X	X	X	X	5000 visits
	E-newsletters	# of subscriptions			X	X			8
	General press releases	# of publications	X	X	X	X	X	X	4

	Social networks memberships	# of followers	X	X	X	X	X		200 followers
	Digital and printed materials (folders)	# produced	X	X	X	X	X		2

This report consists of 1 main chapter, aside from the introduction and conclusion: Chapter 2 presents the D&C channels and activities.

All the project's partners will employ a range of means to disseminate UPWARDS concepts and results. This includes, but not limited to, an online presence, oral and poster presentations, written publications, active contributions to research forums, and workshops.

In addition, workshops with other EU-funded projects working in the same field as the UPWARDS project are to be established. This will create synergies in the dissemination of UPWARDS as the similar projects focus on the aspect of integration of stakeholder feedback among others.

The purpose of this chapter is to present the dissemination actions in detail, listing the activities or outcomes to be carried out throughout the lifetime of the project.

1.2. WP-8 tasks according to the DoA

As stated in the UPWARDS DoA, the main objectives of WP-8 are to assure a good dissemination of the project results in order:

- To create awareness and give visibility and understanding of the project results through a robust, ad-hoc dissemination and communication strategy
- To monitor the achievement of the defined communication objectives
- To adapt the dissemination and communication strategy to each identified type of audience, taking into account its geographical scope and differentiating factors
- To ensure the connection with a broad network of stakeholders external to the consortium.
- To enable the External Expert Advisory Board as a project's multiplier and use envisaged networking activities with other EU projects and EU platforms
- To organize workshops to provide UPWARDS' stakeholders with the project's latest findings and outputs and encourage interaction and knowledge exchange during the project and beyond
- To further develop the initial exploitation strategy/ies defined in section 2.2. To identify innovation processes and future standardization needs. To follow up and suggest innovative policies in the wind energy field.

The dissemination and communication plan (D8.2) is produced as part of the work of WP-8. Through this plan, the project aims at reaching the above-mentioned objectives. This is the result of the contribution of all the partners.

The WP-8 leader (Wavestone) is responsible for the monitoring of all the dissemination activities provided by all the different partners. In order to keep track for these activities, dissemination templates, shown in Annex A, are provided for all partners.

1.3. **Target groups**

UPWARDS expects to have several target groups interested in the results generated throughout the lifetime of the project. Hence, the dissemination activities carried out within the project's lifetime aim at targeting the following groups:

- Policy makers & Standardization bodies
 - These actors will be engaged in high-level, detailed face-to-face talks. This is key as the new technology and the new value chain to be brought forth by the UPWARDS project will become subject of new policies which will then be made public. Thus, these groups will be engaged in talks discussing the impact on and consequences for the wind energy industry, both in the short term and in the long term and how this effort can galvanize further development in the industry and thus what needs to be considered. This will also be important as the results of UPWARDS will impact other industries as well, likely prompting policy adaptations for these respective industries.
- The European network: other projects dealing wind turbine technological development, simulation, data gathering, etc.
 - The purpose of knowledge sharing with this group will be to discover and implement synergies together that will be mutually beneficial, augmenting the impact of each project. This can include face-to-face meetings, sharing of reports, results, survey, etc. Projects under the SET-plan will be given priority in this regard.
- Associations, specifically with international associations or working groups related to the wind industry
 - Articles, press releases and association events will be the main channels to generate awareness and interest in the activities of the UPWARDS project. Those partners of the UPWARDS project as leaders in the various associations concerned will leverage their position to further promote the project and the future impacts it will bring to the industries.
- Industries related to turbine construction, fluid flow simulation, atmospheric modelling, etc.
 - Actors in the wind turbine industry will of course be engaged, such as turbine manufacturers, wind farm developers and operators, as they will be future beneficiaries of the results of the upwards project as they lie further downstream in the value chain. Other industries will also be engaged however due to the possible cross applications of what will result from the UPWARDS project, such as the aerospace, automotive and naval sectors. As such, participation in technology/industry conferences will occur as well as publications in various industry channels. These interactions are to be done in order to propose and prepare future mutually beneficial partnerships that can have further stimulus on the European economy.
- Community stakeholders
 - Shall be engaged using offline and online channels (as described in the previous section) in order to gain both qualitative and quantitative informational feedback. In addition, this will help further increase online media coverage. This will be done to optimize the results of the project while at the same time increase awareness and popularity among the public of wind energy as a key sustainable energy source.
- Scientific community (fluid dynamics, material sciences, atmospheric sciences, acoustics & vibration, etc.)
 - The low TRL range of this project necessitates the communication with and inclusion of, where appropriate, members of the scientific community outside the consortium. The technological tools being created with inevitably have impacts on other fields of research. Thus, to properly exploit this multiplier effect submissions will be made to

peer-reviewed publications, workshops/seminars will be organized and scientific events attended. This will be done to exploit results of the project in the (relative) short term.

- Interested media professionals (especially in the renewable energy, specifically the wind energy field)
 - In accordance with the intent to maximize exposure of the UPWARDS project, media organizations focused on the renewable energy industry will be approached to leverage their reach.

A different dissemination strategy will apply to each group, and these are summarized later on in Table 2.

2. Dissemination & Communication Plan

UPWARDS will use the Zenodo depository (zenodo.org) to store all data which are released for free access. Zenodo is a free large capacity platform for the exchange and curation of research data managed by CERN established as a result of the OpenAIRE project. Zenodo has built in functionality to meet most FAIR criteria and to generate searchable metadata (see section **Error! Reference source not found.**).

In Zenodo data is stored in records with associated metadata. All data must be associated with a community. For that purpose, a "UPWARDS H2020 Project" community has been established that all data from UPWARDS will be associated to. In addition, data will be associated to other communities as the "Wind Energy" community.

2.1. Dissemination & Communication Routes

2.1.1. Online Presence: Project Website & Social Media

The first access point for the general public to UPWARDS is through the project's website available at <https://www.upwards-wind.eu/>. The project's website is considered as one of the main vehicles to disseminate the project's results and to have interaction with the general public.

The main goals of the project website are to:

- Provide information on the project's status, progress, and outcomes
- Provide news on the projects events
- Provide access to public publications and public deliverables

The website is meant to serve as a 'billboard' promoting the project, as well as a source for news & progress on the project, a repository for easy access for the scientific and technical publications that will be made (and can be shared). It is also meant to highlight the consortium's partners. It serves as one of the main channels of communication between the consortium and the general public. As such the website will allow the gathering of measurables used to inform the project's D&C KPIs.

A brief description of each of the partners involved in the project is included on the website, as well as a summary description of their involvement and a link to their respective websites.

In order to boost online and media presence, social media networks will be leveraged in conjunction with the project website. Links to the project page on online networks such as Facebook & LinkedIn are to be part of the website and likewise links to the website will be provided on these network pages. The goal is to improve coordination of dissemination and communication of information across various websites/platforms by the various partners involved in the consortium.

Any updates and/or content (originally posted on the website) that can be adapted and promoted on the online networks shall be posted therein. The network pages, like the website are to updated regularly.

2.1.2. Newsletters & Press Releases

Field Code Changed

Furthermore, regular newsletters and press releases will be regularly released. This will be done in coordination with the various partners to enable a multiplier effect for promotion of the project. Last but not least, general presentations at the local level: surveying will be carried out in order to implement feedback from local actors.

2.1.3. Publication of Journal Articles

The aim of this activity is to disseminate results and information to the scientific committee. Many of the partner organizations, especially the academic and research institutions, published some of the project's scientific results in selected peer-reviewed journals and in conference proceedings. It is often that the results will first be presented at conferences, and then, later on, in journals, presenting a more complete description of the models and results.

Some of the targeted peer-review journals are:

- Wind Energy
- Renewable Energy
- Sustainable Development
- Applied Energy
- Energy conversion & management
- Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments
- Journal of the Energy Institute
- Sustainable Cities & Society

2.1.4. Scientific Conferences

The aim is to present some of the project results, as posters or oral presentations, in major conferences in the field. Some possible conferences are:

- Wind & Energy Conference
- Green Energy & Expo
- Wind Energy Science Conference
- EAWE: European Academy of Wind Energy

2.1.5. Technical Exhibitions

The objective of this activity is to disseminate the knowledge/products to industrial and public authorities by participating in technical exhibitions. The projects main results were distributed through the form of flyers and brochures. Creating flyers, posters, brochures, or research briefs about research projects and findings offer a concise and visually-appealing way to disseminate information to broad audiences. Some possible exhibitions are:

- AWEA Offshore
- EGSA Tradeshow and Standards & Codes
- Brazil WindPower
- APPA Congresso
- TWEC 2018 (Turkish Wind Energy Congress)
- Wind Energy 2018 in Hamburg

2.1.6. Workshops

UPWARDS shall organize 2 stakeholders' workshops, one in M22 and another in M42. The workshops shall gather EU projects focused on the same topic as UPWARDS with the aim of sharing good practices and lessons learned.

Additionally, UPWARDS shall also work to be part of workshops with the aim of showing demonstrations and presenting project results, such as, AWEA Wind Resource and Energy Assessment Workshop

2.1.7. Interaction with other EC-funded Projects/Clusters

The UPWARDS project will seek out links and interaction with other European Commission funded projects in the areas of wind turbine technology simulation, development, adoption and design.

The objective is to create potential synergies with the other projects and exploit opportunities for future research or business ventures. This can also be done through workshops.

Furthermore, European Commission (EC) online tools, such as Horizon Magazine, Project stories, etc. shall be leveraged as well as EU platforms to capitalise on the broad outreach of the EU initiatives of which UPWARDS partners.

2.1.8. Films, Videos and Brochures

The objective is to promote the project's key achievements results through creating videos/films and/or brochures

2.2. Overview of the Communication Strategies and Target Groups

Identification number in the dissemination plan	Dissemination Activity	Dissemination material / type	Target Audience					
			Industry	Researchers / Higher Education	General audience/ Civil society groups	Engineers/Investors Third Parties/Vendors	Policy makers	EU Commission
1	Project Website	general information project results relevant news	x	x		x	x	x
2	Participating in Technical Conference / Exhibitions	technical data Flyers posters	x	x		x		
3	Participating in Scientific Conference	Scientific results (oral presentations; posters)		x		x		

4	Organizing workshops	technical and scientific results	x			x	x
5	Publishing in scientific journals	scientific results		x		x	
6	European Clusters/consortiums	share information create synergies	x	x		x	x
7	Forums/Newsletters/ Technical guides	information/results	x	x		x	
8	Films/ Videos/ Media briefings	information/promotion	x			x	x

3. Data Security

Refer to the Data Management Plan (deliverable D1.4) for details.

4. Conclusions

Dissemination & Communication of the UPWARDS project is being done with both the relevant professional communities and the wider public. This information is being shared at the appropriate level of technical and confidential details for each group respectively.

The dissemination and communication of information will occur over various channels including the project website, social media pages, events, conferences and more. Furthermore, it shall be done, with Wavestone as the lead partner, in coordination with all the partners involved as they can and will be able to promote the project through their own channels as well as through redistribution of any promotional materials including press releases, videos and newsletters.

An approach is in place to obtain feedback from each group (based on the information shared) as per WP8 tasks in order to be considered for integration into the final design of future wind turbines.

The feedback from each group is to be collected through various ways including through polls and surveys that can be properly done on social media networks.

Finally, this Dissemination and Communication Plan will be updated regularly as the project advances.

5. Annex A

Grant Agreement N°763990

UPWARDS
Deliverable DX.X
Deliverable Title

WP	XX	XXX
Task	XX	XXX

Dissemination level¹	XX	Due delivery date	XX/XX/XXXX
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Lead beneficiary	XXX
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Document Version	Date	Author	Comments ³

¹ Dissemination level: PU = Public, PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)
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UPWARDS_DX_MX_vX

Deliverable abstract

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Deliverable Review

		Reviewer #1: /Coordinator			Reviewer #2:		
		Answer	Comments	Type*	Answer	Comments	Type*
1. Is the deliverable in accordance with							
(i) The Description of Work?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(ii) The International State of the Art?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not applicable for this deliverable		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Not applicable for this deliverable	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
2. Is the quality of the deliverable in a status							
(i) That allows it to be sent to European Commission?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(ii) That needs improvement of the writing by the originator of the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(iii) That needs further work by the Partners responsible for the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a

* Type of comments: M = Major comment; m = minor comment; a = advice

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UPWARDS

Presentation templates and logo

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Logo files exists in two variants

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05/18/2018 2

Logo colour and font

- The font used in the logo is Arial narrow bold
- Colors in RGB and CMYK as follows

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